

Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2025; Issue #09: Commentary on

Boström, K. et al.

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2025 papers by Boström, K. et al., Talking about desire to die: Talking past each other? A framework analysis of interview triads with patients, informal caregivers, and health professionals., published in Palliative & Supportive Care.

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Boström et al. offer valuable insight into the dynamics of communication surrounding a profoundly sensitive end-of-life topic: the desire to die. Through semi-structured interviews with seriously ill adult patients, their informal caregivers, and multi-professional health staff, the authors conducted a rigorous framework analysis, identifying four key interpretative themes: reception of open communication, shared reality, content that makes death understandable, and communication strategies. Ultimately, they delineated three distinct communicative types, each bearing direct relevance for clinical practice.¹

The “Between the Lines” type, marked by avoidance and emotional withdrawal, often leads to discontent and unspoken suffering, making it a scenario that may benefit most from proactive, empathetic outreach by clinicians. The “Matter of Fact” type, while seemingly efficient, emphasizes practical matters and risks overlooking latent desires to die. The “Past Each Other” type reflects well-intentioned yet misaligned communication strategies that fragment dialogue and contribute to exclusion.

This study presents a novel perspective on how communication can either enable or obstruct meaningful engagement with dying, surfacing neglected aspects of discussing death in life-limiting conditions while prompting critical questions and a re-examination of current practices.

But what happens when the patient is a child?

In pediatric palliative care (PPC), taboos surrounding death are stronger, making end-of-life conversations even more difficult. Although PPC is grounded in patient- and family-centered care that emphasizes openness and the active involvement of the child to foster understanding and shared decision-making,^{1,2} these ideals are frequently constrained by prognostic uncertainty,

parental difficulty in accepting incurability, and the child's cognitive or developmental stage. Cultural norms, emotional stakes, and protective instincts to shield the child from suffering add further complexity, often delaying or preventing disclosure.

Yet evidence consistently shows that this exclusion, though well-intentioned, can cause confusion, anger, and isolation.³ Children often sense when information is withheld, and many are aware of their impending death even if adults remain silent.⁴ Sensitive, age-appropriate conversations can instead promote alignment between the child's awareness and their lived reality, helping to reduce emotional conflict and preserve trust in caregivers.⁵

The above communication types seem to resonate powerfully also with PPC. A "Between the Lines" approach may manifest as parental reticence, leaving the child to interpret non-verbal cues and unanswered questions. This situation can create a harmful complicity with clinicians that hinders transparency and open communication. A "Matter of Fact" style may emerge when clinicians, focusing on treatment logistics, inadvertently overlook the child's or family's existential fears. The "Past Each Other" type maps onto situations where all parties wish for openness but pursue it through divergent strategies: parents may filter information; clinicians may favor direct disclosure. At the same time, children may alternate between seeking and avoiding clarity.

Recognizing these communication patterns can help professionals move toward more empathetic and constructive dialogues—even in the face of death.

Therefore, PPC professionals play a critical role as interpreters and mediators in facilitating open and appropriate discussions about death and dying by: (1) exploring the child's willingness to

engage, recognizing that silence does not necessarily indicate disinterest; (2) exploring caregivers' wishes and rationale regarding disclosure; (3) navigating tensions between parental fears of harm and the child's right to information; (4) supporting both parents and children through these conversations with concrete emotional tools and personalized strategies; and (5) relieving families of the responsibility to protect one another or remain in fixed roles, thereby enabling trust and mutual understanding.

Each dialogue should reflect the child's age, the family's beliefs, and communication preferences, with discussions prioritizing the child's best interests and tailoring information to their desire. Guiding principles include beneficence, non-maleficence, respect for autonomy, and cultural sensitivity. Honesty—aligned with the child's readiness and the family's capacity to engage, and framed in hope for living as well as possible— is essential. Support should be continuous and non-directive, respecting family dynamics while guiding parents through conversations and preparing for the child's emotional responses. Communication must unfold as an evolving process over time rather than as a singular disclosure. The timing, frequency, intensity, and content of these conversations should empower the family, following individualized decisions about whether and how to engage the child. To equip clinicians for this complex work, specialist training and ongoing supervision are indispensable.

ⁱ The authors aimed to investigate communication types involved when talking about death and the desire to die. Through a triangled perspective (patient, caregiver, clinician), they identified three types and highlighted their limits. The key point is to make clinicians aware of these possible complex dynamics to prevent their negative consequences. They indeed report: "We do not consider it a problem that we did not identify a type with 'perfect' communication (i.e., including health professionals, informal caregivers, and patients, perceived as open and

satisfying and resulting in correct transmission of information and completely shared reality). Rather, we suggest that even instances of “failed” communication in our results support the notion of communication as always co-constructed and interpretative: people are simultaneously sender and receiver in a process of mutual influence."

Additional References

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